

Synthesis and structural characterization of Schiff base complexes of Pd^{II}, Rh^{III} and Ru^{III}

B. H. Mehta* and J. A. Shaikh

Department of Chemistry, University of Mumbai, Vidyanagari, Santacruz (E), Mumbai-400 098, India

E-mail : bipin_281050@yahoo.com

Manuscript received 16 April 2008, revised 19 January 2009, accepted 12 February 2009

Abstract : A bidentate ligand, 2-hydroxy-1-naphthalidene-4'-nitroaniline (HNNA) was synthesized from 2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde and 4-nitroaniline. Its metal complexes of general formula M(HNNA)₂ where M = Pd^{II} and [M(HNNA)₂X.H₂O].2H₂O where M = Rh^{III} and Ru^{III} and X = Cl have been prepared. All the complexes were characterized using various physico-chemical methods such as elemental analysis, thermal analysis and spectral (IR, electronic and NMR) analysis. The Rh^{III} and Ru^{III} complexes have octahedral structures while Pd^{II} complex has square planar geometry.

Keywords : Schiff base, 2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde, 4-nitroaniline, Pd^{II}, Rh^{III} and Ru^{III} complexes.

Introduction

Schiff bases are in general veryable coordinating ligands and metal complexes derived from Schiff bases occupy an important position in the development of coordination chemistry, as observed from their synthesis, structure, reactivity and physico-chemical properties¹. Transition metal complexes of azomethines have witnessed a great deal of interest in the recent years because of their chemical, pharmacological^{2,3} and analytical applications⁴. In addition, the presence of nitrogen and oxygen donor atoms in the complexes act as stereospecific catalyst for many reactions like oxidation⁵, reduction⁶, hydrolysis and possess antibacterial activity^{7,4}. Keeping in view the importance of platinum group metals^{8,9}, we have synthesized and characterized the complexes of Pd^{II}, Rh^{III} and Ru^{III} of Schiff base derived from 2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde and 4-nitroaniline.

Results and discussion

The complexes of Rh^{III} and Ru^{III} were synthesized using metal : ligand, 1 : 3 mole ratios but complexes indicate 1 : 2 stoichiometry. All the complexes are stable in air, non hygroscopic, colored solids and decompose at higher temperature at (>300 °C). The complexes are insoluble in water and sparingly soluble in common organic solvents like ethanol, methanol, chloroform, carbon tetrachloride, petroleum ether etc. but soluble in DMF and DMSO. The analytical and physical data of ligand and metal complexes are reported in Table 1.

IR spectra : Free Schiff base showed a strong absorption at 1620 cm⁻¹ characteristic of $\nu_{C=N}$. This band is shifted to lower wave number to the extent of 20–40 cm⁻¹ in the spectra of all complexes indicating the coordination of Schiff base through azomethine nitrogen to the metal atom. IR spectrum of ligand shows strong band in the region 3450–3200 cm⁻¹, which is assigned to hydrogen bonded ν_{O-H} stretching vibration¹⁰. The spectra of Ru^{III} and Rh^{III} complexes exhibited a broad absorption band in the region of 3400–3200 cm⁻¹ with weak intensities attributed to ν_{O-H} stretching vibration of the coordinated water molecule¹¹ which is substantiated by the observance of an absorption band at 830 cm⁻¹. The increase in absorption frequency of phenolic ν_{C-O} band occurring in 1400–1360 cm⁻¹ in free ligand to 1340–1278 cm⁻¹ in metal complexes indicates that another coordination site in Schiff base is phenolic oxygen¹². IR spectra of complexes exhibit new bands in 525–505 and 480–440 cm⁻¹ regions assigned to ν_{M-N} and ν_{M-O} stretching vibrations respectively^{13,14}.

¹H NMR spectra : The ¹H NMR spectra of Schiff base and its complexes were recorded in DMSO. The absence of hydroxyl protons (δ 14.21 ppm) in the spectra of metal complexes indicates deprotonation of the hydroxyl proton due to coordination of oxygen to the metal. The signals of azomethine were found in the range of 10.00–12.00 ppm downfield compared to its Schiff base (δ 9.64 ppm) after complexation to the metal ion inferring coordination

Ligand/Complexes (M.W.)	Color	M.p. (°C)	Elemental analysis (%) :				
			Found (Calcd.)				
			C	H	N	Cl	Metal
$C_{17}H_{12}N_2O_3$ (292.00)	Orange red	225	69.82 (69.86)	3.89 (4.10)	9.23 (9.58)	-	-
$PdC_{34}H_{22}N_4O_6$ (688.42)	Yellow	>300	58.42 (59.26)	3.52 (3.19)	8.20 (8.13)	-	15.22 (15.45)
$RhC_{34}H_{24}N_4O_7Cl.2H_2O$ (774.40)	Brown	>300	52.57 (52.68)	2.95 (3.61)	7.28 (7.23)	4.80 (4.58)	13.52 (13.28)
$RuC_{34}H_{24}N_4O_7Cl.2H_2O$ (772.27)	Brown	>300	52.42 (52.81)	3.28 (3.26)	7.19 (7.25)	4.30 (4.59)	12.82 (13.08)

through azomethine nitrogen atom. The aromatic protons appeared as multiplet in the δ 6.50–8.50 ppm range.

Fig. 1. 1H NMR spectra of (i) ligand, (ii) $Pd(HNNA)_2$, (iii) $[Ru(HNNA)_2Cl.H_2O].2H_2O$.

Electronic absorption spectra : Electronic spectrum of ligand showed three high intensity bands lying at 28923, 28902 and 31348 cm^{-1} assigned to the $n \rightarrow \pi^*$ and $\sigma \rightarrow \sigma^*$ transition. The electronic spectrum of Pd^{II} complex display bands at 18450 and 27700 cm^{-1} which may be assigned to $^1A_{1g} \rightarrow ^1B_{1g}$ and $^1A_{1g} \rightarrow ^1E_{1g}$ transition. The band occurring at 31546 cm^{-1} in UV region is ascribed as charge transfer transition. Hence, a square planar geometry may be assigned for Pd^{II} complex¹⁵.

The electronic spectrum of Rh^{III} complex exhibits two broad bands at 22320 and 29940 cm^{-1} which have been assigned to $^1A_{1g} \rightarrow ^1T_{1g}$ and $^1A_{1g} \rightarrow ^1T_{2g}$ transitions respectively¹⁶. The band appearing at 15270 cm^{-1} is assigned to the $^1A_{1g} \rightarrow ^3T_{1g}$ transition and the other band appearing at 38480 cm^{-1} is a charge transfer transition. The Rh^{III} complex may be assigned octahedral geometry¹⁷.

Table 2. Spectral data

Ligand/ Complexes	IR (cm^{-1})					Electronic spectral data		1H NMR (δ ppm)
	ν_{O-H}	$\nu_{C=N}$	ν_{C-O}	ν_{M-N}	ν_{M-O}	(cm^{-1})	Assignment	
$C_{17}H_{12}N_2O_3$	3434	1620	1398	-	-	28923	$n \rightarrow \pi^*$	14.21 (s, OH)
						28902	$\sigma \rightarrow \sigma^*$	9.64 (s, CH=N)
						31348		6.9–8.5 (m, Ar)
$PdC_{34}H_{22}N_4O_6$	-	1602	1278	517	485	18450	$^1A_{1g} \rightarrow ^1B_{1g}$	10.2 (s, CH=N)
						27700	$^1A_{1g} \rightarrow ^1E_{1g}$	6.6–8.8 (m, Ar)
						31546	Charge transfer	
$RhC_{34}H_{24}N_4O_7Cl.2H_2O$	3351	1584	1336	510	487	15270	$^1A_{1g} \rightarrow ^3T_{1g}$	10.8 (s, CH=N)
						22320	$^1A_{1g} \rightarrow ^1T_{1g}$	6.5–8.5 (m, Ar)
						29940	$^1A_{1g} \rightarrow ^1T_{2g}$	
						38480	Charge transfer	
$RuC_{34}H_{24}N_4O_7Cl.2H_2O$	3338	1598	1334	512	473	18994	$^2T_{2g} \rightarrow ^2A_{2g}$	10.7 (s, CH=N)
						28985	Charge transfer	6.5–8.9 (m, Ar)

Table 3. Thermal data

Complexes	TGA data Observed (Calcd. %)		
	Water content		
	Water of crystallization	Coordinated water	
$\text{PdC}_{34}\text{H}_{22}\text{N}_4\text{O}_6$	–	–	83.50 (84.24)
$\text{RhC}_{34}\text{H}_{24}\text{N}_4\text{O}_7\text{Cl}\cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$	5.00 (4.65)	2.81 (2.32)	80.46 (79.74)
$\text{RuC}_{34}\text{H}_{24}\text{N}_4\text{O}_7\text{Cl}\cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$	4.90 (4.66)	2.52 (2.33)	80.68 (79.92)

The ground state of Ru^{III} (t_{2g}^5 configuration) is ${}^2T_{2g}$ and the first excited doublet levels in the order of increasing energy are ${}^2A_{2g}$ and ${}^2T_{1g}$ which arise from $t_{2g}^4 e_g^1$ configuration. In most of the Ru^{III} complexes, the electronic spectra show only charge transfer bands^{18,19}. Since in a d^5 system and especially in Ru^{III} which has relatively high oxidizing properties, the charge transfer bands in the lower energy region obscure the weaker $d-d$ transitions. However, the band at 18994 cm^{-1} has been assigned to the ${}^2T_{2g} \rightarrow {}^2A_{2g}$ transition based on the low extinction coefficient value (ϵ) compared to charge transfer band at 28985 cm^{-1} . This is in conformity with the assignments made for similar other octahedral Ru^{III} complexes²⁰.

Thermal analysis : The thermal decompositions of the complexes were studied using the TG and DTG technique. The thermogram of Rh^{III} and Ru^{III} complexes shows the first endothermic weight loss between $60\text{--}80\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ which may be attributed to the elimination of two molecules of water of crystallization²¹. The second weight loss step between $175\text{--}200\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ may correspond the elimination of coordinated water molecule. The third weight loss step between $250\text{--}450\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ may be attributed to the loss of organic moiety and a molecule of chlorine. The final decomposition leaves a mixed residue of $\text{Ru}_2\text{O}_3\text{--RuO}_2$ for Ru^{III} complex and Rh_2O_3 for Rh^{III} complex at $580\text{--}600\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$.

The thermogram of Pd^{II} complex does not show such significant loss indicating absence of any lattice water or water of crystallization as it is thermally stable upto $200\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. With further increase in the temperature, the mass loss continued with decomposition of ligand finally resulting in corresponding PdO residue at $550\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. The thermal data for the complexes are shown in Table 3.

Conclusion : On the basis of analytical and spectral studies, Pd^{II} complex has been found to exhibit square planar structure whereas Rh^{III} and Ru^{III} complexes have displayed octahedral geometry as :

Fig. 2. Proposed structures of metal complexes.

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of A.R. grade. 2-Hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde was obtained from Fluka chemika. Metal salts were obtained from S. D. Fine chem. Ltd. Distilled solvents were used throughout the experiments.

Preparation of ligand : The Schiff base ligand was prepared by condensing equimolar amount of 2-hydroxy-

Note

l-naphthaldehyde with 4-nitro aniline in ethanol. The reaction mixture was refluxed for 5 h and the resulting solution was concentrated and then cooled. The solid product so separated was filtered, washed, recrystallised and dried when orange red crystals were obtained, m.p. 225 °C; yield 75%.

Preparation of the complexes : The metal complexes were synthesized by refluxation-precipitation method. The hot ethanolic solution of ligand (0.002 mol for Pd^{II} and 0.003 mol for Rh^{III} and Ru^{III}) was mixed with ethanolic solution of palladium chloride (0.177, 0.001 mol), rhodium trichloride (0.207, 0.001 mol) and hydrated ruthenium chloride (0.261, 0.001 mol) respectively and the resulting mixture was refluxed for two hours on water bath. Solid precipitate of Pd^{II} and Rh^{III} were obtained at pH 4.0 and 8.5 respectively by dropwise addition of ethanolic solution of ammonia. In case of Ru^{III}, the pH was adjusted to 9.5 using ethanolic ammonia solution, volume reduced to 1/4th of its original volume and poured in ice cold water. The complexes were filtered, washed with hot water, then with hot ethanol and dried in oven at 120 °C.

Physical measurements : The melting points of all the complexes were determined by open capillary method. Elemental analysis was carried out in the Micro-analytical Laboratory, IIT Powai, Bombay. The metal content for the metal complexes were determined on ICP-8840 Plasma lab supplied by LABTAM, Australia. The complexes were examined for solubility using polar and non-polar solvents. The electronic absorption spectra of ligands and complexes were recorded in the UV-Visible region using DMSO as solvent on UV-Visible 2100 spectrophotometer (Perkin-Elmer-Lambda-25). IR spectra was recorded using KBr pellets on FTIR 4200 (Shimadzu Corporation). ¹H NMR spectra were obtained from Mercury Plus 300 MHz, NMR spectrophotometer.

References

- 1 Z Shirin and R N Mukherjee, *Polyhedron*, 1992, 20, 2625
- 2 V M Leovac, V Drvakovic, D Petrovic, G Argay and A Kalman, *Polyhedron*, 1983, 2, 1307
- 3 S Padhye and G B Kauffman, *Coord Chem Rev* 1985, 63, 127
- 4 R B Singh and H Ishii, *Critical Reviews in Analytical Chemistry*, 1991, 22, 381
- 5 R I Kureshy, N H Khan, S H R Abdi, S T Patel and P Iyer, *J Mol Catal*, 1999, 150 175
- 6 Y Aoyama, J T Kujisawa, T Wananawe, A Toi and H Ogashi, *J Am Chem Soc* 1986, 108, 943
- 7 T Daniel Thangadurai and K Natarajan, *Indian J Chem , Sect A*, 2002, 41, 741
- 8 M K Biyala, N Fahmi and R V Singh, *Indian J Chem , Sect A*, 2005, 43, 2536
- 9 I Pal, F Basuli and S Bhattacharya, *Proc Indian Acad Sci (Chem Sci)*, 2002, 114, 255
- 10 L N Sharda and M C Ganorkar, *Indian J Chem , Sect A*, 1988, 27, 617
- 11 C N Rao and J R Ferraro, "Spectroscopy in Inorganic Chemistry", Vol 10, Academic Press, New York, 1970
- 12 B H Mehta and D S Joishar, *Asian J Chem*, 2004, 16, 910
- 13 A M El-Hendawy and A H Alkubaisi, *Polyhedron*, 1993, 12, 2343
- 14 S Vats and L M Sharma, *Synth React Inorg Metal-Org Chem*, 1997, 27, 1565
- 15 S Chandra and R Singh, *Indian J Chem Sect A*, 1988, 27 417
- 16 E Bertelli, C Preti and G Tosi, *J Inorg Nucl Chem*, 1975, 37, 1421
- 17 C K Jorgenson, "Absorption Spectra and Chemical Bonding in Complexes", Pergamon Press, New York, 1964, p 183
- 18 A B P Lever, "Inorganic Electronic Spectroscopy", 2nd ed, Elsevier, New York, 1984
- 19 G Venkatachalam, S Maheswaran and R Ramesh, *Indian J Chem , Sect A*, 2005, 44, 705
- 20 T Daniel Thangadurai, M Gowri and K Natarajan, *Synth React Inorg Metal-Org Chem* 1997, 32, 329
- 21 F A El-Saed, R M El-Bahnasawy, M A Azzem and A K El-Sawaf, *Polyhedron*, 1994, 13, 1781